

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of electronic word of mouth (E-WOM) and Influencer Marketing on Sariayu Martha Tilaar Cosmetics Purchase Decision Through Brand Image as Mediating Variable (Study on Sariayu Martha Tilaar Consumers in Jakarta)

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Abstract

The cosmetics industry in Indonesia continues to increase, which makes business competition in this field even tighter. This makes local cosmetic brands compete in setting marketing strategies to increase consumer purchasing decisions. This study aims to determine the effect of electronic word of mouth and influencer marketing on purchasing decisions for Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products through brand image as a mediating variable. This type of research is explanatory research with a quantitative approach. The sample of this study is 100 respondents who are determined using non-probability sampling techniques, namely purposive sampling and accidental sampling. This study uses Partial Least Square (PLS) data analysis techniques through SmartPLS 4. The data collection technique is carried out through distributing questionnaires. This study shows that electronic word of mouth and influencer marketing have no significant effect on purchase decisions. Electronic word of mouth and influencer marketing have a significant effect on brand image and brand image has a significant effect on purchase decisions. Brand image fully mediates the effect of electronic word of mouth and influencer marketing on purchase decisions. Based on the result of this research, Sariayu Martha Tilaar needs to encourage consumers to give good electronic word of mouth and apply good influencer marketing to build the company's brand image which then can increase consumer purchase decision.

Keywords: Brand Image; Electronic Word of Mouth; Influencer Marketing; Purchase Decision

1. Introduction

The advancement of technology and information is currently growing rapidly and has made the internet an integral part of people's daily lives. Referring to the We Are Social report, as of January 2024, internet users in Indonesia have penetrated 66.5% of the population or the equivalent of 185 million individuals have gained access to the internet. This encourages the dissemination of information to be so fast and easy, one of which is the dissemination of information about the importance of maintaining appearance. The use of cosmetics provides an opportunity for users to change their appearance to encourage self-confidence (1). This makes cosmetics one of the products needed by consumers. In 2023, the cosmetics industry in Indonesia increased by 21.9% with a total of 1,010 from the previous 913 in 2022 (2).

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Figure 1 Sales Data of Cosmetics Companies Listed on the IDX

Based on data from Databoks, from five cosmetic companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, Martha Tilaar (PT Martina Berto) occupies the fifth position with sales value of IDR 24.8 billion per month or IDR 297.22 billion per year in 2020. As one of the long-established companies in the cosmetics industry, Martha Tilaar's sales value is the lowest and has not even reached half a trillion throughout 2020.

Figure 2 Sales Data of Sariayu Martha Tilaar Cosmetic Products (annual report)

Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetics sales experienced a drastic decline of 65.46% in 2021 with total sales of IDR 65,948,000,000 from the previous year with total sales of IDR 190,944,000,000. This happened because of the Covid-19 pandemic which had an impact on reducing consumer purchasing power for products. In 2022, the sales of Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetics again experienced a considerable increase to more than 100% of the total sales in the previous year. However, in 2023, the total sales of Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetics decreased again by 20.65%. This shows that there is a fluctuation with a downward trend in the sales of Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products, which indicates a problem in consumer purchasing decisions for Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products.

One of the factors that influence purchasing decisions is consumer confidence in buying a product after consumers know the exact information about the product(3). Electronic word of mouth can facilitate consumers in getting real information about a product or service because it is given directly by other consumers who have already obtained the product or service (4). Electronic word of mouth can assist consumers in finding supporting data related to a product because it contains assessments shared by other buyers based on their experiences after using the product.

Another factor that influences consumers in making purchasing decisions is psychological factors, one of which is perception (5). Perception is closely related to the image of a brand or brand image, this is in line with (6) who say brand image is a consumer's perception of a brand formed from associations that arise in the minds of consumers. Even though it has been established since the 1970s, Sariayu Martha Tilaar is known as a cosmetic brand that continues to make modern innovations in creating cosmetic products, so that its products remain relevant in following beauty trends among Indonesian women. Even so, Sariayu Martha Tilaar still has to improve its brand image so that it can still compete in the market and increase consumers' purchasing decisions for its products.

2. Study Literature

2.1. Consumer Behavior

Consumer behavior defined as the study of individual, organizational, and group actions in choosing, buying, and using product or service ideas in satisfying consumer needs and wants (6).

2.2. Purchase Decision

Purchase decisions defined as consumer decisions in choosing which brand to buy after evaluating alternative factors (7). Indicators of purchasing decisions, namely steadiness in buying products, habits in buying products, providing recommendations to others, and making repeat purchases.

2.3. Electronic Word of Mouth

Electronic word of mouth (E-WOM) is informal communication that is non-commercial and occurs online regarding consumer opinions about a good or service (8). Indicators of electronic word of mouth, namely intensity, positive opinions, and content.

2.4. Influencer Marketing

Influencer marketing is the process of identifying and activating individuals who have influence over a specific target audience to be part of a product campaign, so as to increase reach, sales, and engagement with consumers (9). Indicators of influencer marketing namely popularity, credibility, attractiveness, and power (10).

2.5. Brand Image

Brand image is consumer perceptions and beliefs about a brand that are reflected in the associations embedded in the minds of consumers (6). Brand image indicators, namely strength, uniqueness, and excellence.

3. Method

This type of research is explanatory research which aims to test the proposed hypothesis and is expected to explain how electronic word of mouth and influencer marketing influence purchasing decisions through brand image. The population of this study are buyers and users of Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products in Jakarta. The sample of this study was 100 respondents who were determined using non-probability sampling techniques, namely purposive sampling and accidental sampling. This research uses Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) techniques through the SmartPLS 4 program to test the hypothesis.

Figure 3 Hypothesis Model

- H1: There is an influence of electronic word of mouth on purchase decisions
- H2: There is an influence of influencer marketing on purchase decisions
- H3: There is an influence of electronic word of mouth on brand image
- H4: There is an influence of influencer marketing on brand image
- H5: There is an influence of brand image on purchase decisions

- H6: There is an influence of electronic word of mouth on purchase decisions through brand image
- H7: There is an influence of influencer marketing on purchase decisions through brand image

4. Result

In this study, the electronic word of mouth, influencer marketing, and brand image variables are multidimensional constructs formed from dimensional latent constructs so that the validity test will be carried out in two stages, namely first order construct and second order construct analysis. In the first order construct analysis, the dimensional latent construct will be reflected by its indicators. Furthermore, in the second order construct, the construct will be reflected by its dimensional latent construct.

Table 1 Convergent Validity

	Electronic Word of Mouth			Electronic Word of Mouth	Type (as defined)	Description	
	Intensity	Positive Opinion	Content				
First Order Construct							
EWOM1				0,814	Reflective	Valid	
EWOM2				0,842	Reflective	Valid	
EWOM3				0,792	Reflective	Valid	
EWOM4				0,818	Reflective	Valid	
EWOM5				0,798	Reflective	Valid	
EWOM6				0,763	Reflective	Valid	
EWOM7				0,772	Reflective	Valid	
EWOM8				0.782	Reflective	Valid	
Second Order Construct							
EWOM1	0,899				Reflective	Valid	
EWOM2	0,875				Reflective	Valid	
EWOM3	0,917				Reflective	Valid	
EWOM4		0,899			Reflective	Valid	
EWOM5		0,894			Reflective	Valid	
EWOM6			0,843		Reflective	Valid	
EWOM7			0,878		Reflective	Valid	
EWOM8			0,846		Reflective	Valid	
	Influencer Marketing			Influencer Marketing		Type (as defined)	Description
	Popularity	Credibility	Attractiveness	Power			
First Order Construct							
IM1				0,782	Reflective	Valid	
IM2				0,804	Reflective	Valid	
IM3				0,812	Reflective	Valid	
IM4				0,742	Reflective	Valid	
IM5				0,709	Reflective	Valid	

IM6					0,764	Reflective	Valid
IM7					0,805	Reflective	Valid
IM8					0,752	Reflective	Valid
IM9					0,782	Reflective	Valid
Second Order Construct							
IM1	0,923					Reflective	Valid
IM2	0,927					Reflective	Valid
IM3		0,912				Reflective	Valid
IM4		0,894				Reflective	Valid
IM5			0,813			Reflective	Valid
IM6			0,863			Reflective	Valid
IM7			0,891			Reflective	Valid
IM8				0,893		Reflective	Valid
IM9				0,901		Reflective	Valid

	Brand Image			Brand Image	Type (as defined)	Description
	Strenghtness	Uniqueness	Favorable			
First Order Construct						
B11				0,732	Reflective	Valid
B12				0,724	Reflective	Valid
B13				0,733	Reflective	Valid
B14				0,787	Reflective	Valid
B15				0,786	Reflective	Valid
B16				0,777	Reflective	Valid
B17				0,728	Reflective	Valid
B18				0,781	Reflective	Valid
Second Order Construct						
B11	0,830				Reflective	Valid
B12	0,782				Reflective	Valid
B13	0,809				Reflective	Valid
B14		0,903			Reflective	Valid
B15		0,903			Reflective	Valid
B16			0,884		Reflective	Valid
B17			0,847		Reflective	Valid
B18			0,829		Reflective	Valid

	Purchase Decision	Type (as defined)	Description
First Order Construct			
KP1	0,801	Reflective	Valid
KP2	0,716	Reflective	Valid
KP3	0,780	Reflective	Valid
KP4	0,887	Reflective	Valid

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Table 2 Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Score

	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
First Order Construct	
Electronic Word of Mouth	0,637
Influencer Marketing	0,598
Brand Image	0,572
Purchase Decision	0,637
Second Order Construct	
Intensity	0.805
Positive Opinion	0.804
Content	0.732
Popularity	0.856
Credibility	0.815
Attractiveness	0.733
Power	0.805
Strengthness	0.652
Uniqueness	0.816
Favorable	0.729

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Table 1 shows that the outer loading value of all items from both first order and second order testing has a value greater than 0.7 (> 0.7). Thus, it can be said that the latent dimensional constructs acceptable because the indicators are represented. Furthermore, Table 2 shows that each construct has an AVE value greater than 0.5 (>0.5). Thus, it can be said that the convergent validity of the first order construct and second order construct which includes four variables is declared valid.

Table 3 Discriminant Validity

First Order Construct						
	Electronic Word of Mouth	Influencer Marketing	Brand Image	Purchase Decision	Type defined) (as	Description
EWOM1	0.814	0.473	0.504	0.200	Reflective	Valid
EWOM2	0.842	0.438	0.525	0.143	Reflective	Valid
EWOM3	0.792	0.415	0.493	0.157	Reflective	Valid

EWOM4	0.818	0.435	0.562	0.097	Reflective	Valid
EWOM5	0.798	0.416	0.583	0.106	Reflective	Valid
EWOM6	0.763	0.581	0.643	0.037	Reflective	Valid
EWOM7	0.772	0.536	0.574	0.223	Reflective	Valid
EWOM8	0.782	0.518	0.527	0.085	Reflective	Valid

Second Order Construct

	Electronic Word of Mouth	Dimension of Electronic Word of Mouth			Type (as defined)	Description
		Intensity	Positive Opinion	Content		
EWOM1	0.814	0.899	0.660	0.621	Reflective	Valid
EWOM2	0.842	0.917	0.678	0.661	Reflective	Valid
EWOM3	0.792	0.875	0.678	0.577	Reflective	Valid
EWOM4	0.818	0.694	0.899	0.674	Reflective	Valid
EWOM5	0.798	0.648	0.894	0.674	Reflective	Valid
EWOM6	0.763	0.581	0.640	0.843	Reflective	Valid
EWOM7	0.772	0.600	0.601	0.878	Reflective	Valid
EWOM8	0.782	0.594	0.689	0.846	Reflective	Valid

First Order Construct

	Electronic Word of Mouth	Influencer Marketing	Brand Image	Purchase Decision		Type (as defined)	Description
IM1	0.389	0.782	0.507	0.171		Reflective	Valid
IM2	0.409	0.804	0.557	0.102		Reflective	Valid
IM3	0.494	0.812	0.533	0.251		Reflective	Valid
IM4	0.376	0.742	0.471	0.323		Reflective	Valid
IM5	0.487	0.709	0.479	0.245		Reflective	Valid
IM6	0.520	0.764	0.627	0.170		Reflective	Valid
IM7	0.545	0.805	0.543	0.173		Reflective	Valid
IM8	0.454	0.752	0.498	0.309		Reflective	Valid
IM9	0.475	0.782	0.557	0.192		Reflective	Valid

Second Order Construct

	Influencer Marketing	Dimension of Influencer Marketing			Power	Type (as defined)	Description
		Popularity	Credibility	Attractiveness			
IM1	0.782	0.923	0.670	0.588	0.556	Reflective	Valid
IM2	0.804	0.927	0.654	0.601	0.634	Reflective	Valid
IM3	0.812	0.677	0.912	0.640	0.611	Reflective	Valid
IM4	0.742	0.612	0.894	0.548	0.556	Reflective	Valid
IM5	0.709	0.485	0.543	0.813	0.551	Reflective	Valid

IM6	0.764	0.563	0.548	0.863	0.605	Reflective	Valid
IM7	0.805	0.597	0.603	0.891	0.638	Reflective	Valid
IM8	0.752	0.569	0.530	0.631	0.893	Reflective	Valid
IM9	0.782	0.586	0.629	0.625	0.901	Reflective	Valid

First Order Construct						
	Electronic Word of Mouth	Influencer Marketing	Brand Image	Purchase Decision	Type defined) (as	Description
BI1	0.513	0.580	0.732	0.358	Reflective	Valid
BI2	0.558	0.617	0.724	0.288	Reflective	Valid
BI3	0.553	0.458	0.733	0.349	Reflective	Valid
BI4	0.603	0.570	0.787	0.280	Reflective	Valid
BI5	0.553	0.451	0.786	0.316	Reflective	Valid
BI6	0.547	0.493	0.777	0.174	Reflective	Valid
BI7	0.386	0.409	0.728	0.215	Reflective	Valid
BI8	0.453	0.564	0.781	0.408	Reflective	Valid
Second Order Construct						
	Brand Image	Dimension of Brand Image			Type defined) (as	Description
		Strengthness	Uniqueness	Favorable		
BI1	0.732	0.830	0.505	0.594	Reflective	Valid
BI2	0.724	0.782	0.581	0.557	Reflective	Valid
BI3	0.733	0.809	0.640	0.516	Reflective	Valid
BI4	0.787	0.648	0.903	0.595	Reflective	Valid
BI5	0.786	0.639	0.903	0.604	Reflective	Valid
BI6	0.777	0.588	0.572	0.884	Reflective	Valid
BI7	0.728	0.547	0.524	0.847	Reflective	Valid
BI8	0.781	0.625	0.600	0.829	Reflective	Valid
	Electronic Word of Mouth	Influencer Marketing	Brand Image	Purchase Decision	Type defined) (as	Description
First Order Construct						
KP1	0.252	0.330	0.368	0.801	Reflective	Valid
KP2	0.058	0.051	0.155	0.716	Reflective	Valid
KP3	0.055	0.136	0.197	0.780	Reflective	Valid
KP4	0.110	0.253	0.412	0.887	Reflective	Valid

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Based on table 3, it is known that each indicator on all variables in this study has a greater cross loading value with each construct than its correlation value with other constructs. This indicates that the discriminant validity of the four variables has been fulfilled.

Table 4 Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
First Order Construct		
Electronic Word of Mouth	0.918	0.933
Influencer Marketing	0.916	0.930
Brand Image	0.893	0.914
Purchase Decision	0.821	0.875
Second Order Construct		
Intensity	0.878	0.925
Positive Opinion	0.755	0.891
Content	0.817	0.891
Popularity	0.832	0.923
Credible	0.774	0.898
Attractiveness	0.817	0.892
Power	0.758	0.892
Strengthness	0.733	0.849
Uniqueness	0.774	0.899
Favorable	0.814	0.890

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Table 4 presents data on the results of reliability testing. From the table, it is known that the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values of all indicators of the variables are greater than 0.7 (> 0.7). This shows that the instruments used in this study are reliable.

Table 5 R-Square

	R-Square
Brand Image	0.594
Purchase Decision	0.182

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Based on table 5, it is known that the brand image variable obtained an R-Square value of 0.594, which means that the electronic word of mouth and influencer marketing variables have a moderate influence on the brand image variable by 59.4% and the remaining 40.6% is influenced by other variables outside this study. The purchase decision variable obtained an R-Square value of 0.182, which means that the electronic word of mouth, influencer marketing, and brand image variables have a weak influence on the purchase decision variable by 18.2% and the remaining 81.8% is influenced by other variables outside this study.

Table 6 F-Square

	Brand Image	Electronic Word of Mouth	Influencer Marketing	Purchase Decision
Brand Image				0.129
Electronic Word of Mouth	0.304			0.030

Influencer Marketing	0.288			0.002
Purchase Decision				

Source: processed primary data, 2024

F-Square has 3 value categories, namely the small category if it has a value smaller or equal to 0.02, the medium category if the value is greater than or equal to 0.15, and the strong category if the value is greater than or equal to 0.35 (11). Based on table 6, it is known that:

- Electronic word of mouth has small effect on purchase decision with an F-Square value of 0.030.
- Influencer marketing has a small effect on purchase decision with an F-Square value of 0.002.
- Electronic word of mouth has a moderate effect on brand image with an F-Square value of 0.304.
- Influencer marketing has a moderate effect on brand image with an F-Square value of 0.288.
- Brand Image has small effect on purchase decision with an F-Square value of 0.129.

Table 7 Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	T-Statistics	P-Values	Conclusion
Direct effect				
Electronic Word of Mouth -> Purchase Decision	-0.224	1.264	0.206	H1 Rejected
Influencer Marketing -> Purchase Decision	0.060	0.390	0.696	H2 Rejected
Electronic Word of Mouth -> Brand Image	0.437	4.246	0.000	H3 Accepted
Influencer Marketing -> Brand Image	0.426	4.336	0.000	H4 Accepted
Brand Image -> Purchase Decision	0.510	2.769	0.006	H5 Accepted
Indirect Effect				
Electronic Word of Mouth -> Brand Image -> Purchase Decision	0.223	2.128	0.033	H6 Accepted (full mediation)
Influencer Marketing -> Brand Image -> Purchase Decision	0.217	2.322	0.020	H7 Accepted (full mediation)

Source: processed primary data, 2024

Hypothesis testing is done by observing the T-Statistics and P-Value values through bootstrapping calculations using 5000 subsamples. The hypothesis is accepted if the t-statistics value is greater than the t-table score of 1.96 and the P-value is smaller than 0.05. Based on table 7, it is known that the results of hypothesis testing in this study show that H1 is rejected negatively and insignificantly while H2 is rejected positively, but not significantly. Then H3, H4, H5, H6, and H7 are accepted positively and significantly.

5. Discussion

From the consumer's point of view, electronic word of mouth serves as a basis for gathering important information to help the purchasing decision process (12). This study proves that electronic word of mouth does not have a significant

influence on purchase decision. Although consumers think that electronic word of mouth about Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products can help consumers in building judgments regarding these products, it is still unable to significantly influence consumer purchase decisions for these products. The results of this study are in line with the research of Khairuna & Satrio (2024) which states that electronic word of mouth has no effect and is not significant to purchase decision.

An influencer is considered attractive to a brand because it has popularity that comes from a high level of expertise and connection with its audience (13). This study shows that influencer marketing does not have a significant influence on purchase decision. This means that consumers do not make influencer figures the basis for making purchase decision. These results are in line with Mahendra & Edastama (2022) which states that influencer marketing has no significant influence on purchase decision.

Electronic word of mouth is an assessment given by other customers on the internet, where good electronic word of mouth can create a good brand image in the eyes of consumers (14). The better the electronic word of mouth given, the higher the brand image will be. This is in line with the research of Semuel & Lianto (2014) which states that the higher the electronic word of mouth given by respondents causes a high brand image. This study proves that electronic word of mouth has a positive and significant influence on brand image. Respondents considered that electronic word of mouth given by other consumers regarding Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products influenced respondents' views on Sariayu Martha Tilaar products. This result is in line with Widyawati (2017) research which shows that electronic word of mouth has a significant effect on brand image.

Influencers who have a strong influence on their audience can help boost a company's brand image. An influencer can create a better brand image and bring in potential customers by utilizing their followers on social media (15). The results of previous studies support the results of this study which show that influencer marketing has a positive and significant influence on brand image. Based on this, it can be interpreted that the information conveyed by influencers about Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products has formed a good brand image of Sariayu Martha Tilaar for consumers.

A good brand image can increase consumer purchasing decisions for the brand. This is because a good brand image will create a positive impression of a brand in the minds of consumers and encourage consumers to purchase products (16). The results of this study are in line with the research of Luthfi et al. (2022) which shows that brand image has a positive and significant influence on purchase decision. The higher the brand image of Sariayu Martha Tilaar, the higher the consumer purchase decision for Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products.

One of the stages in making a purchase decision is active information search, where consumers seek information about a need through reading materials and online information before finally deciding to make a purchase (6). In this case, electronic word of mouth provides information about a product provided by other consumers about the product on the internet based on their experience after using the product. Electronic word of mouth spread on the internet has a strong influence on brand image and later encourages consumer purchase decision (17,18). In this study, the results of the direct test show that electronic word of mouth has no significant effect on purchase decision, while the indirect test shows that electronic word of mouth has a significant effect on purchase decision through brand image. It can be concluded that brand image fully mediates the relationship between electronic word of mouth and purchase decision.

In deciding to purchase cosmetics, consumers often seek information through influencers on social media because influencers are considered a personalized, authentic, and credible source of information (18). In this case, influencers can influence purchasing decisions with their power to provide information about the advantages of a brand. Influencer marketing has a greater influence on consumer purchase decision when the brand image is positive (19). In this study, the direct test results show that influencer marketing does not have a significant influence on purchase decisions, while the indirect test results show that influencer marketing has a significant influence on purchase decision through brand image. This shows that brand image can fully mediate the relationship between influencer marketing and purchase decision.

6. Conclusions

- Electronic Word of Mouth does not have a significant influence on the Purchase Decision variable with t-statistics $1.264 < t\text{-table } 1.96$ and p-value $0.206 > 0.05$. This shows that electronic word of mouth about Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products does not have a strong influence on consumer purchase decisions on these products.
- Influencer Marketing has no significant influence on Purchase Decision variable with t-statistics $0.390 < t\text{-table } 1.96$ and p-value $0.696 > 0.05$. This means that influencer marketing by Sariayu Martha Tilaar does not have a

strong influence on consumer purchase decision on the product.

- Electronic Word of Mouth has a significant influence on Brand Image variable with t-statistics 4.246 > t-table 1.96 and p-value 0.000 < 0.05. This shows that good electronic word of mouth about Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products can improve Sariayu Martha Tilaar brand image. Respondents feel that electronic word of mouth given by other consumers on the internet can build Sariayu Martha Tilaar brand image in consumers' mind.
- Influencer Marketing has a significant influence on Brand Image variable with t-statistics 4.336 > t-table 1.96 and p-value 0.000 < 0.05. This shows that good influencer marketing about Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products can increase Sariayu Martha Tilaar brand image. Respondents feel that Sariayu Martha Tilaar's influencers give influence to its audience in providing information that can encourage consumers' assessment of Sariayu Martha Tilaar.
- Brand Image has significant influence on Purchase Decision variable with t-statistics 2.769 > t-table 1.96 and p-value 0.006 < 0.05. This shows that the better the brand image of Sariayu Martha Tilaar will encourage consumer purchase decision for Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products. Respondents feel that a good brand image creates a good brand perception for consumers so that consumers are interested in buying Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products.
- Electronic Word of Mouth has a significant influence on the Purchase Decision variable through the Brand Image variable with t-statistics 2.128 > t-table 1.96 and p-value 0.033 < 0.05. The results of this study indicate that electronic word of mouth has a significant effect on brand image and brand image has a significant effect on purchase decision. This shows that good electronic word of mouth for Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products can influence Sariayu Martha Tilaar's brand image and then encourage consumer purchase decision for Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products.
- Influencer Marketing has a significant influence on Purchase Decision variable through Brand Image variable with t-statistics 2.322 > t-table 1.96 and p-value 0.020 < 0.05. The results of this study indicate that influencer marketing has a significant effect on brand image and brand image has a significant effect on purchase decision.

Recommendations

- Sariayu Martha Tilaar can increase electronic word of mouth by encouraging consumers to give ratings about Sariayu Martha Tilaar cosmetic products because the more good ratings will affect consumers' views on the product. This is expected to improve Sariayu Martha Tilaar's brand image and encourage consumers to buy the product.
- Sariayu Martha Tilaar can improve its influencer marketing by giving the selected influencers an understanding of the company's vision, mission and values so that the influencers can share information that is in line with the company. This is expected so that influencers can provide more information to the audience so that later it can influence consumers' views on the product.
- Sariayu Martha Tilaar's strengths that need to be improved so that consumer perception of Sariayu Martha Tilaar is getting better. Sariayu Martha Tilaar can develop product innovations that are different from other cosmetic brands so that this can highlight the uniqueness of Sariayu Martha Tilaar with other brands.
- Sariayu Martha Tilaar can implement a referral program that gives rewards or discounts for consumers who invite others to buy its products. One of the examples is giving discount for the second product purchase. Related to this, Sariayu Martha Tilaar can provide product information that is complete, relevant, and easily accessible by consumers to increase the purchase decision of its cosmetic products.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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